

Market needs and priorities assessment

Milestone 20

W W W . S U R F S A F E P R O J E C T . E U

This document covers the market needs and priorities assessment of industrial players and advice on strategies to become an effective potential provider for the industry. This will give UPORTO the necessary tools to engage in collaborative research with industry and translate academic principles into applied solutions, tackling not only funding sustainability but also boosting the true societal relevance of the research groups.

Contextualization:

Much academic research is carried out in very controlled laboratory systems in order to determine the effect of single parameters on surface hygiene. However, the translation of such academic knowledge into industry is very difficult for several reasons. One of the most important factors is that the experimental work carried out in laboratories is not representative of the environmental scenario that is found in industry. In addition, the processing of any food in an industrial scenario is extremely complex, hence more than one parameter needs to be tested at the same time. Testing and understanding how a variety of factors influence one another is not what scientists are taught to investigate; they are taught to examine only one parameter at a time, yet such an approach is imperative for this type of translational work. In order to give UPORTO the necessary tools to engage in collaborative research with industry and translate academic principles into applied solutions, some key aspects need to be considered to enable the translation of their research into technology readiness levels that industrial partners and businesses will find engaging. This will result in funding sustainability and boosting the societal relevance of the research groups.

Within the overall scope of SurfSAFE, enhancing relationships (and future contracts) with the industry may be the most ambitious outcome for the project. Indeed, despite the effective knowledge and research capabilities that will be improved throughout the project, the strategic positioning facing industrial needs and opportunities will support the long-term sustainability of research groups. In particular, for UPORTO, a critical aspect to attain and promote collaboration with the industry is understanding their needs. This is an important point since private funding of research activities (generally speaking for all engineering research groups) actually holds an increasing share of the whole funding at the national level. Hence, boosting national/international collaborations with relevant and committed industries is essential.

The innovative research under the SurfSAFE concept is expected to generate major breakthroughs to manage biofilm formation and bacterial resistance, bringing new solutions to improve cleanability in the food industry.

The UPORTO needs to improve its positioning and level of integration in the National, Regional, and European "relevant markets" for up-taking the R&D results in this field. Therefore, management of innovation is needed, which includes IP management, research, and development in the translation of academic knowledge into industrial sectors, safe and effective regulatory systems, the ability to produce new products with high standards of quality, a national distribution system in both the public and private sectors and international distribution systems and trade-in technologies.

KEY PLAYERS:

Internationally, some of the main industry stakeholders include the Processing & Packing Machinery Association (PPMA) in the field of equipment manufacturing; Diversey and Ecolab in the field of cleaning solutions for the food industry; and Nestlé, Danone, Unilever Mondelez International Inc., Groupe Lactalis SA, Mars Inc., Ferrero SpA, Arla Foods, PepsiCo, and Tetrapak, among others, in the food industry [1].

In order to devise strategies to become effective potential providers for such industries, significant work is required to formulate plans for the translation of the research and development technology so that the industry can instantly see the benefit. Often, the foremost industrial needs include demonstration of an increase in profit, justification of the investment which will be supported by shareholders, that is, the return on investment, fast translation of academic know-how into industrial practice, and rapid increase in technology readiness levels.

THE PLAN:

The first question that should be addressed by UPORTO is what is the unique selling point (USP) of academic knowledge that they wish to translate into an industrial process. It needs to be made very clear, how the academic knowledge from UPORTO is better than the current alternative solutions already on the market. In addition, it is key to know what the current competitor products are already available in the market, and why this novel idea is better, particularly if the new knowledge comes at a higher cost. The company will also want to know how knowledge increases the productivity of the industry and how it will reduce costs and/or provide more sustainable alternative solutions already available. It needs to be very clear to the industry that new knowledge is distinguished from current competitor solutions.

Key questions within the plan to be addressed should include the research results so that the proof of concept of new academic knowledge can be evidenced. Scientific publications may demonstrate the validity of the proof-of-concept at this point to support the idea of new knowledge in the industry. This can be difficult because some industries like to see their technology backed up by journal publications, while others prefer to keep intellectual property undisclosed. This can lead to IP issues which will be discussed later. The technological readiness level of knowledge needs to be clearly demonstrated. The cost to the manufacturer of the new knowledge needs to be determined, particularly if the new product will be manufactured to scale. Consideration needs to be given to any regulations, standards, authorisations, etc., that are required before the knowledge is used in a full-scale industrial plant.

Other questions that need to be addressed before approaching an industry or company include how long it will take for the transfer of knowledge to be fully usable. Issues surrounding technology transfers and intellectual property, including patents and licencing, must be defined. Additionally, the identification and mapping of risks related to exploitation must be thoroughly explored.

TARGETING THE MARKETS:

In order to target the correct markets, due diligence should be carried out to determine the market trends, for example, if the new knowledge has value and can be translated into the size of the industrial plant that is being collaborated with. Also, the location of the industry should be considered, as this may affect the regulatory requirements. In terms of competitors, it is advantageous to know their strengths and weaknesses, so that the new industries that are approached can provide information on any new knowledge to demonstrate to the industry the advantages of the new knowledge and why the industry should invest in academic knowledge.

Branding should also be considered; for example, if the industry can be pointed towards a professional and easy-to-use website, the answers to questions they might have can enforce the validity of new knowledge and showcase articles, patents, and regulatory and sustainability accreditations. Many websites demonstrate poor delivery of what they are trying

to sell. Very simple solutions can include using animations for pictures because they are very eye-catching and bold, and explain what knowledge the industry will be receiving. The website should be extremely easy to navigate and, if possible, have reviews and links to other social media. Central to marketing is often the story behind the brand and the inclusion of an FAQ page. At this stage, the inclusion of a person with marketing and sales expertise might be advisable.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (IP):

The IP status of the knowledge transfer must be very clear. Within IP policies, issues may be raised. Taking this into account, an established knowledge transfer agreement between partners is essential, and it must represent a benefit for all parties. It may be beneficial to have an IP audit to determine whether there are already patents that cover a similar IP. Licencing agreements should also be considered, and exploration of the available licencing agreements should be carried out because there are several different types of agreements.

COSTS:

The cost of implementing the new knowledge must be clearly laid out and includes the costs for all regulatory and other authorisations required. The financial plan must demonstrate how new knowledge meets both industrial needs and results in a return on investment for the industry. Costs should also include an estimation to implement any planned activities and to estimate the eventual price of knowledge transfer. In addition, consideration needs to be given to whether the implementation of new knowledge will result in a return in revenue to the University. The background knowledge of all these facets will help give UPORTO the necessary tools to engage in collaborative research with the industry and translate academic principles into applied solutions.

With respect to sustainability and societal relevance, there is currently much emphasis on sustainability and green economy. There is a key need for industries to demonstrate that they are implementing green and sustainable solutions, which decrease such factors as energy use, water use, chemical effluent discharge into water systems, etc. Such factors have both sustainable and societal effects, which can be emphasised by new knowledge processes. Such factors that could be highlighted include the development of new products towards a Sustainable Circular Economy, whereby the United Nations, in 2015, set out a 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development plan, which included environmental issues, quality, and sustainability. In addition, the EU is investing in green initiatives that improve air and water quality, which include creating an effective circular economy (where products are designed to be more durable, reusable, repairable, recyclable, and energy-efficient). These factors are currently important for industry, and knowledge that helps implement such solutions may be of value.

Reference:

[1] <https://www.columbusglobal.com/en-gb/blog/food-industry-trends-for-2023>, assessed on 26 June 2023.

